

Cultural Competency Among ABA Practitioners in Orange County, CA

by

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Abstract

The issue of cultural competency among professionals in applied behavior analysis (ABA) is understood to be essential, but setting specific standards and guidelines has yet to be developed. Furthermore, the region-specific demographic data of board-certified behavior analysts (BCBAs) and ABA therapists is not publicly available. Therefore, it is difficult to determine if the needs of culturally and linguistically diverse children and families receiving ABA care are met. To understand cultural competency practices among ABA practitioners in Orange County, California, this research study aimed to describe the demographic characteristics of ABA professionals and assess their training and comfort levels for working with diverse children and their families. An anonymous survey was distributed to BCBAs and ABA therapists in Orange County. Results found that the participants' demographics loosely aligned with the demographics of the population served and that most participants held a Master's degree. The majority of participants reported only sometimes being taught culturally competent practices and wished they were better prepared to work with diverse children and their families. Most participants also felt comfortable working with diverse children and their families. The implications of these findings are discussed in addition to recommendations for incorporating culturally competent practices in the field of ABA.

Cultural Competency Among ABA Practitioners in Orange County, CA

The United States is experiencing rapidly increasing numbers of minority populations. Data from the latest national census analyzed the makeup of the U.S. population, revealing a much more diverse America than was previously thought. Specifically, Jones and colleagues (2021) reported that almost all groups experienced population gains from 2010-2020, except the White Non-Hispanic population, which decreased by 8.6%. Furthermore, the multiracial population, consisting of people of two or more races, grew by a staggering 276% (Jones et al., 2021). As the U.S. continues to represent a more diverse population, the demand for culturally competent and sensitive therapists, educators, healthcare, and government workers is also expected to increase. One location of interest is Orange County, CA, where the population already consists of nearly equal numbers of White Non-Latinx (38.5%) and Latinx (34.1%) individuals (United States Census Bureau, n.d.). Given these recent shifts in demographics, this research study aimed to understand cultural competency (or the lack thereof) in the field of applied behavior analysis (ABA) by surveying local (Orange County, CA) ABA therapists on their knowledge, practices, and demographic characteristics as they related to cultural competency.

Autism Spectrum Disorder

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder that is evident in early childhood and comprised of two core areas of impairment: 1) persistent impairment in social communication and interactions and 2) restricted or repetitive behavior and/or thought patterns (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). One in 44 children has ASD, and there has been a rapid increase in the prevalence of ASD over the past 30 years (Maenner et al., 2021). As indicated in the name, ASD exists on a spectrum, meaning that there is great variability between

individuals with an ASD diagnosis. Their symptoms can range widely, from having mild to severe challenges in the two core domains. Even though terms such as “low functioning” and “high functioning” are often used to describe the spectrum, they can be misleading, as the support needs vary for each individual (Fisher et al., 2021). Regardless of their symptom severity, many individuals with ASD can reach their goals and become productive and contributing members of society with the help of skills gained through early intervention, such as applied behavior analysis (ABA) (Fisher et al., 2021).

Applied Behavior Analysis

Applied behavior analysis (ABA) “focuses on solving problems of social importance using the principles and procedures of behavior analysis” (Fisher et al., 2021, p. 3). Based on fundamental principles and concepts of behavior, ABA is used to increase desirable behaviors, decrease undesirable behaviors, and treat specific learning and developmental disorders. One of the most common conditions that ABA therapy is used to treat is ASD.

In the ABA field, there is an absence of required training to increase cultural competency among practitioners (Conners & Capell, 2020). This absence persists despite the emphasis placed by the Behavior Analyst Certification Board (BACB) Professional and Ethical Compliance Code that practitioners should receive the necessary education when working with diverse families (Luna et al., 2023). While some data are available (Behavior Analyst Certification Board, 2022), more research about the cultural competency knowledge and demographics of practitioners in the field of ABA is vital to assess the necessity of increased training in this area. This understanding will inform how to incorporate culturally relevant and sensitive practices into the treatment.

Cultural Competence in ABA

The term **culture** refers to the ways in which people of various backgrounds and with diverse identities experience the world around them. Everyone holds values and beliefs they have been taught; nobody is “culturally-neutral.” Additionally, culture is not abstract; it is always present and can be experienced first-hand (Fong & Tanaka, 2013). Behavior analysts must be able to understand their own culture(s) before they can observe and analyze the behaviors of others (Fong & Tanaka, 2013). The term **competence** refers to the ability to do something efficiently and successfully (American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language, 2011). Thus, **cultural competence** is defined as “a set of congruent behaviors, attitudes, and policies that come together in a system, agency or among professionals and enable that system, agency or those professions to work effectively in cross-cultural situations” (Fong & Tanaka, 2013, p. 18). Further, culture evolves over time. Therefore, cultural competency guidelines should be adapted with cultural shifts.

To best serve the children and families they work with, ABA therapists must recognize their clients’ diversity while carefully examining the role of culture in goal setting and treatment delivery (Fong et al., 2017). In addition, negative stereotypical images of minorities held by clinicians can influence the diagnostic and treatment options they provide (Fong et al., 2017). This is significant because negative biases can directly influence the type and quality of treatment, which has implications for the long-term outcomes of individuals with ASD from minority populations. ABA therapists must be able to recognize any biases they hold about particular groups of people before they begin treating these individuals.

To better understand the needs in the field, Beaulieu et al. (2019) assessed how much training in working with diverse populations that Board Certified Behavior Analysts (BCBAs) received in their schooling. The researchers sent an email to a BACB list to collect information

on their demographics, education levels, employment characteristics, and comfort and skill levels regarding working with individuals from diverse backgrounds. Most respondents said that training for working with diverse families was very important and reported feeling comfortable working with diverse populations. However, few had received training in working with diverse individuals (Beaulieu et al., 2019). Similarly, other researchers have noted that access to data on cultural diversity coursework in behavior analytic programs is hard to come by (Deochand & Costello, 2022), providing further evidence of a lack of cultural competency training in the ABA field.

Another issue that needs to be addressed is the withholding of demographic data on BCBAAs. In an article addressing several barriers to ABA treatment for culturally and linguistically diverse (CLD) families, Dennison et al. (2019) stated that several attempts were made to request demographics from BCBA certificate holders. However, the BACB never responded or shared this information. Because of this, the number of CLD behavior analysts available to work with CLD families in need is not clear (Dennison et al., 2019). Since the publication of this article, the BACB has posted certificate holder demographic data on its website (Behavior Analyst Certification Board, 2022). However, there continues to be a lack of published region-specific demographic data. This is a paramount issue, particularly in areas like Southern California where populations are largely diverse; the first step in addressing the cultural competency of behavior analysts starts with rectifying this deficit.

Moreover, the BACB and the field of ABA recognize that diversity, multiculturalism, and cultural competency are vital. Yet, no explicit standards for working with diverse families exist. With clear guidelines, clinicians could more effectively work with clients and their families (Connors & Capell, 2020). Based on evidence from past studies on cultural competency

within the field of ABA, further research is warranted to address the lack of professional training for working with diverse families.

Other fields (e.g., nursing) have utilized surveys to assess cultural competency among practitioners (Xu et al., 2016). For example, Xu and colleagues created a multicultural nursing competence survey instrument to assess undergraduate student nurses. The researchers found validity in their instrument and showed the survey methodology was appropriate for assessing cultural competency among clinicians. This study informed cultural competency among nurses and can serve as an example for other fields. Using this model, the current study utilized survey methodology to gather demographic information and cultural competency among BCBAAs and ABA therapists in Orange County, CA.

The location of interest for the present study, Orange County, CA, was targeted because of the researcher's personal affiliation with the area, both educationally and occupationally. In addition, Orange County is made up of a diverse population, with the three largest ethnic groups in 2020 being White Non-Hispanic (39.8%), Asian Non-Hispanic (20.9%), and White Hispanic (17.8%) (Data USA, n.d.). Results from this study have the potential to inform future studies with aims to evaluate the cultural competency of ABA therapists throughout the country.

Problem Statement, Research Aims, Objectives, & Questions

Problem Statement

The field of ABA does not specify how practitioners can meet the needs of diverse children and families (Connors & Capell, 2020). Furthermore, the region-specific demographics of Board Certified Behavior Analysts (BCBAAs) are not made publicly available (Dennison et al., 2019). Without set standards regarding cultural competency in the field of ABA, practitioners may not be implementing culturally competent and sensitive techniques into treatment plans. As

the population of the United States becomes increasingly diverse, those working with children and families must be competent in understanding various cultural backgrounds and how they may influence behavior.

Research Aims, Objectives, & Questions

The aim of this research was to gather demographics on BCBAs and ABA therapists in Orange County, CA, in addition to information on their training and comfort levels working with diverse families. This information is vital in determining if the needs of diverse families are being met through ABA services. Additionally, the study aims to spread awareness about the significance of cultural competency in the field of ABA and propose ways in which ABA agencies can improve the cultural competency of their practitioners. As a result of this study, local ABA agencies can begin to recognize the importance of establishing standards for their professionals regarding cultural competency. To address these aims, the study had the following objectives:

1. To describe the demographic characteristics of BCBAs in Orange County, CA.
2. To evaluate Orange County BCBAs' cultural competency training and comfort levels in working with culturally diverse children in families.
3. To offer solutions for ABA agencies in Orange County, CA, regarding the maximization of the cultural competency of its practitioners.

More specifically, the following research questions were assessed:

1. What are the demographics of ABA therapists/BCBAs in Orange County, CA?
2. How much training did these therapists receive on cultural competency and working with diverse families?

3. How comfortable do they feel working with culturally diverse families?
4. How often, and in what ways, do they incorporate culturally sensitive practices?

Methods

To address the research questions, a survey was distributed to obtain primary quantitative and qualitative data about BCBA's and ABA therapists' demographics, training, and comfort levels working with diverse children and their families.

Participants & Setting

Participants were recruited via email to ABA agencies affiliated with the California State University, Fullerton's (CSUF) Center for Internships and Community Engagement (CICE), and to other ABA agencies in Orange County, California. Those who did not respond to the email, or did not have an email listed on their website, received a phone call or a voicemail. The emails and phone calls briefly explained the study's purpose and asked if the person of contact would be willing to send the anonymous survey to the BCBA's and ABA therapists who work at their agency. Emails, phone calls, and voicemails were sent to twenty-five ABA agencies. Of the twenty-five agencies contacted, only five agreed to participate. Ultimately, thirty-six participants were included in the analysis and results. Thirty-six respondents answered the demographic questions, twenty-five respondents answered the questions pertaining to how often and in what ways they incorporate culturally sensitive techniques into their practice, and twenty-one respondents answered the questions pertaining to levels of training, education, and comfortability relating to cultural competency and working with diverse families. This study was approved by CSUF's Institutional Review Board (IRB). The survey was completed online via the Qualtrics website through an anonymous link.

Materials

Distributed through Qualtrics, the survey consisted of nineteen multiple-choice questions and questions using a five-point Likert scale to obtain demographic data and gain insight into participants' training and comfort levels working with diverse children and their families.

Demographic questions included items such as age, gender identity, race, etc.

Questions on participants' training and comfort levels were adapted from the *Self-Assessment Checklist for Personnel Providing Services and Supports to Children and Youth with Special Health Needs and Their Families* (Goode, 1989). This questionnaire was designed to heighten the awareness and consideration of personnel to the importance of cultural and linguistic competence in health, mental health, and human service settings. Example items included "I display pictures, posters, and other materials that reflect the cultures and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by my program or agency," "For children who speak languages or dialects other than English, I attempt to learn and use keywords in their language so that I am better able to communicate with them during assessment, treatment, or other interventions," and, "I advocate for the review of my program's or agency's mission statement, goals, policies, and procedures to ensure that they incorporate principles and practices that promote cultural diversity and cultural competence." These items, along with others, were included in the survey. Statements were rated on a scale of one to five, where 1 = *Never*, 2 = *Rarely*, 3 = *Sometimes*, 4 = *Often*, and 5 = *Always*.

Three optional open-ended questions were also included to allow participants to share additional information. These included, "Is there anything else you would like to share about your clinical practice as it pertains to working with culturally/linguistically diverse families?" "Is there anything else you would like to share about your training or education as it pertains to working with culturally/linguistically diverse families?" and "Is there anything else you would

like to share?" Previous studies in other fields (e.g., nursing) have utilized similar methodologies in assessing cultural competency among practitioners (Xu et al., 2016). A copy of the *Self-Assessment Checklist for Personnel Providing Services and Supports to Children and Youth with Special Health Needs and Their Families* (Goode, 1989) can be found in Appendix A. A copy of the survey from the present study can be found in Appendix B.

Procedure

The participant recruitment process occurred over the span of about six months. An email was drafted and sent to the directors of each agency, who had the option of sending the anonymous survey link to BCBA's and ABA therapists at their agency. If there was no response to the email after about a week, a phone call was made to follow up. Some agencies did not answer the phone call, in which case a voicemail was left. Another week was given for the agencies to respond, and a follow-up email was sent if there was still no response. Agencies were not contacted more than three times. The survey data were collected through an anonymous link on Qualtrics and took participants about ten to fifteen minutes to complete.

Data Analysis

The Qualtrics data were exported to SPSS for analysis. First, descriptive statistics were analyzed to evaluate the frequencies associated with the demographic data. Then, the mean and standard deviation were obtained for the other survey questions. Finally, due to a low response rate ($n = 5$), the qualitative items were not formally analyzed. There were 36 respondents on the demographics items, but as the survey progressed, several respondents did not provide answers. Specifically, thirty-six respondents answered the demographic questions, twenty-five respondents answered the questions pertaining to how often and in what ways they incorporate culturally sensitive techniques into their practice, and twenty-one respondents answered the

questions pertaining to levels of training, education, and comfortability relating to cultural competency and working with diverse families. This is reflected in Tables 1, 2, and 3, as well as in the results below.

Results

Demographics of ABA therapists/BCBAs in Orange County, CA

The first research question asked, "what are the demographics of ABA therapists or BCBAs in Orange County, CA?" Table 1 summarizes the demographic information of the participants. Thirty-six participants provided responses on this section of the survey. Most participants identified as Hispanic/Latinx (44.4%) females (88.9%), aged 26-35 years old (44.4%). Thirty-one percent of participants identified as White (non-Hispanic/Latinx), followed by 13.9% identifying as Asian or Asian American. Eleven percent of participants selected multiple races/ethnicities they identified with. No participants identified as Native American or Black/African American. Most respondents reported their highest level of education as holding a master's degree (44.4%), followed by having a bachelor's degree (30.6%), and then an associate degree (16.7%). Only 5.6% of participants reported their education level as completing some college but holding no degree.

ABA therapists/BCBAs' Incorporation of Culturally Sensitive Practices

The second research question used a 5-point Likert scale (i.e., 1 = "never" to 5 = "always") to ask, "How often, and in what ways do ABA therapists/BCBAs in Orange County, CA incorporate culturally sensitive practices?" Table 2 displays the results for this research question. For this section of the survey, twenty-five participants responded. Most participants responded that they "rarely" or "sometimes" displayed pictures, posters, and other materials that reflect the cultures and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by their programs or

agencies ($M = 2.68, SD = 1.25$). When using videos, films, or other media sources for education, treatment, or other interventions, on average participants reported "sometimes" ensuring they reflect the cultures of children and families served by their programs or agencies ($M = 3.80, SD = 1.00$). Participants "rarely" encouraged and provided opportunities for children and their families to share experiences through storytelling, puppets, marionettes, or other props to support the "oral tradition" common among many cultures ($M = 2.64, SD = 1.50$). For children who speak languages or dialects other than English, participants reported, on average, "sometimes" to "often" attempting to learn and use keywords in their language so that they are better able to communicate with them during assessment, treatment, or other interventions. Participants reported "often" when asked about using visual aids, gestures, and physical prompts in their interactions with children who have limited English proficiency ($M = 4.56, SD = 0.58$). When interacting with parents and other family members who have limited English proficiency, participants "often" kept in mind that limitation in English proficiency is in no way a reflection of their level of intellectual functioning ($M = 4.88, SD = 0.44$). On average, participants "often" said they understood the principles and practices of linguistic competency and applied them within their programs or agencies ($M = 4.08, SD = 1.02$). Participants also "often" avoided imposing values that may conflict or be inconsistent with those of cultures or ethnic groups other than their own ($M = 4.72, SD = 0.54$). Participants "sometimes" advocated for the review of their programs' or agencies' mission statements, goals, policies, and procedures to ensure that they incorporated principles and practices that promote cultural diversity, cultural competence, and linguistic competence ($M = 3.88, SD = 1.27$). Finally, participants "often" understood that beliefs about mental illness and emotional disabilities are culturally based and accepted that responses to

these conditions and related treatment/intervention are heavily influenced by culture ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 0.71$).

ABA therapists/BCBAs' Levels of Cultural Competency Training

The final research question asked, "How much training did these therapists receive on cultural competency and working with diverse families?" As depicted in Table 1, the majority of participants held a master's degree (44.4%), followed by a bachelor's degree (30.6%), and then an associate's degree (16.7%). Described in Table 3 are participants' levels of training and education on cultural competency and working with diverse families. Twenty-one respondents answered these Likert response (i.e., 1 = "never" to 5 = "always") survey questions. On average, participants reported that the programs or agencies they work for "sometimes" provide training courses, workshops, or meetings on working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families ($M = 3.00$, $SD = 1.18$). Regarding their education, participants tended to respond that they were "sometimes" taught about culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families, and how to work with them ($M = 3.81$, $SD = 0.98$).

ABA therapists/BCBAs' Comfort in Working with Diverse Families

Table 3 also displays participants' comfort levels working with diverse families. Participants, on average, "sometimes" or "often" felt supported by the programs or agencies they worked for regarding working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.97$). On average, participants also said "often" when asked if they felt comfortable when working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.70$) and that they "sometimes" wished they were better prepared to work with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families ($M = 3.05$, $SD = 1.16$).

Discussion

This study aimed to describe the characteristics of, and cultural competency practices used by, ABA practitioners in Orange County, CA. Specifically, the results provided some insights into the demographics of BCBA and ABA therapists in a particular region of Southern California, information currently unavailable to the public. According to the findings, Orange County BCBA and ABA therapists primarily identify as female and aged 26-35 years old. Most hold a master's or bachelor's degrees, indicating they have ample education. In addition, the results showed that the demographics of the BCBA and ABA therapists surveyed generally represented the demographics of the population they served. For example, in Orange County, the three largest ethnic groups in 2020 were White Non-Hispanic (39.8%), Asian Non-Hispanic (20.9%), and White Hispanic (17.8%) (Data USA, n.d.). The current study found that the three largest ethnic groups of the participants included Hispanic/Latinx (44.4%), White Non-Hispanic/Latinx (30.6%), and Asian or Asian American (13.9%).

Despite most participants holding either 4-year or advanced degrees, they reported only sometimes being taught in their education about culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families and how to work with them. This suggests that educational institutions could better teach about cultural and linguistic competency, what culturally and linguistically competent practices look like, and how to apply them. Additionally, participants stated their programs or agencies sometimes provide training courses, workshops, or meetings on working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families, suggesting that ABA agencies could also do better at providing educational opportunities for their practitioners to learn about cultural and linguistic competency.

Even though they sometimes wish they were better prepared to work with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families, the results also showed that most participants

felt comfortable when working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families. This suggests that additional cultural competency training may be needed to prepare them for certain situations. It may also reflect the participants' lack of support in the field, suggesting that they may prepare themselves for working with diverse families even when their employment agencies do not.

These findings are consistent with previous studies on cultural competency in the field of ABA. For instance, Beaulieu et al. (2019) found that 86% of their respondents reported feeling moderately or extremely skilled in working with diverse individuals, even though most respondents reported having little to no training in working with diverse individuals. It is unclear exactly why ABA practitioners are reporting feeling confident in their work with diverse individuals, given their lack of training, as surveys have not directed questions toward this reasoning. However, it is possible that participants feel comfortable working with diverse children and families despite their lack of training because of their own personal experiences from diverse backgrounds. For example, in the current study, 69.4% of participants reported identifying as either Hispanic/Latinx, Asian/Asian American, or coming from multiple ethnic backgrounds. Nevertheless, one's own ethnic identity is not sufficient to provide culturally competent care.

Lastly, the results offered insight into how often, and in what ways, ABA practitioners incorporate culturally sensitive practices. Participants reported often using aids and prompts in their interactions with children who have limited English proficiency, avoiding imposing values that may be incongruent with others' and keeping in mind that limited English proficiency is not reflective of intellectual functioning among their clients' families. Despite these indicators of cultural competency, rarely did participants display materials depicting the cultures and ethnic

backgrounds of their clients, and infrequently did they encourage and provide opportunities for children and their families to share experiences through traditional methods common among many cultures. These findings suggest that while some culturally and linguistically sensitive techniques are often practiced, others are rarely practiced, showing an inconsistency in application. This could be due to a lack of training, a misunderstanding of the various methods of implementation of cultural and linguistic practices, or a lack of set standards or guidelines from the agencies or programs regarding cultural competency.

Limitations & Implications

The results of this research should be interpreted with caution, noting the study's limitations. First, the findings are based on a small sample. With an extremely specific target population of BCBA's and ABA therapists in Orange County, CA, recruitment of participants proved difficult. Twenty-five ABA agencies across Orange County, CA, were invited to participate in the study, but only five responded that they were willing and interested. This resulted in a total of 36 participants. Furthermore, of the 36 recruited, only 21 participants completed the survey in its entirety, resulting in missing data for some of the questions. It is unclear why some participants started the survey but did not finish, as it was designed to take ten to fifteen minutes to complete. The lack of participants is consistent with previous research, as another study included 703 participants in the analysis and results after sending the invitation to 20,553 BCBA certificate holders (Beaulieu et al., 2019). Future studies should account for this, and generalizations should be made with caution. A shortage of willing participants makes it unclear whether the needs of diverse children and their families receiving ABA care are being met.

Recommendations

The data show inconsistencies in the application of culturally and linguistically sensitive practices. Based on these findings, it is recommended that ABA programs and agencies design explicit standards and guidelines for their BCBA's and ABA therapists. These could take the form of publicly available self-assessment checklists, such as the *Self-Assessment Checklist for Personnel Providing Services and Supports to Children and Youth with Special Health Needs and Their Families* (Goode, 1989) utilized for this research. Self-assessments are an effective way to increase understanding of one's cultural identity, which is the first step to providing culturally competent care (Fong et al., 2017). Standards and guidelines provided to ABA practitioners could also be created by individual ABA agencies. The standards or guidelines should include specific examples of how the BCBA's and ABA therapists will incorporate these techniques so they can comprehend how this might take place in their assessments and treatments (e.g., BCBA's and ABA therapists will attempt to learn about the traditions the family values, and will show an appreciation for them by incorporating them into assessments, treatments, or conversations, when appropriate). Further, with ever-changing population demographics, the standards or guidelines should also be updated frequently to reflect the population served and their needs. Additionally, discussions should be facilitated among BCBA's and ABA therapists so they can ask questions and learn from each other's experiences. This could occur regularly at meetings, conferences, or workshops.

The BACB should also release specific standards and guidelines regarding culturally and linguistically sensitive practices. According to Section 1.07 of the BACB's *Ethics Code for Behavior Analysts* (2020), behavior analysts actively engage in professional development activities to gain knowledge and skills related to cultural responsiveness and diversity by evaluating their own biases and the supervisees' and trainees' biases. However, there are no

specific guidelines for BCBA's and ABA therapists to follow from the BACB. Suppose the BACB were to release explicit guidelines and standards relating to cultural and linguistic competency. In that case, it is likely that more ABA practitioners would implement culturally sensitive strategies and have a better understanding of cultural competency.

Future research is needed to understand ABA practitioners' demographics, training levels, and comfort levels when working with diverse families and how they understand and incorporate culturally and linguistically sensitive practices. These studies could further inform the development of standardized guidelines and training.

Conclusion

In summary, the field of ABA and its practitioners recognize the significance of cultural competency in assessing and treating those receiving ABA therapy. Yet, there needs to be more specific standards and guidelines for ABA practitioners to follow. Furthermore, the region-specific demographic data of BCBA's and ABA therapists is not publicly available. These failings make it challenging to determine if the needs of diverse individuals receiving ABA care are being met. Thus, further study in this area is warranted.

Table 1*Demographic Information of BCBAs and ABA Therapists in Orange County, CA (N = 36)*

	<i>n</i>	%
Gender		
Male	3	8.3
Female	32	88.9
Transgender	1	2.8
Age (years)		
18-25	15	41.7
26-35	16	44.4
36-45	4	11.1
46-65	1	2.8
66 or older	-	-
Race (Select all that apply)		
Black or African American	-	-
White (non-Hispanic/Latinx)	11	30.6
Hispanic/Latinx	16	44.4
Asian or Asian American	5	13.9
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	-	-
Native American	-	-
Multi	4	11.1
Highest Level of Education		
High school graduate, diploma, or the equivalent (e.g., GED)	-	-
Some college, no degree	2	5.6
Trade/technical/vocational training	-	-
Associate degree	6	16.7
Bachelor's degree (BA/BS)	11	30.6
Master's degree (MA/MS)	16	44.4
Doctorate degree (Ph.D./MD)	-	-
Other	1	2.8

Table 2

The Frequency and Ways BCBA's and ABA Therapists in Orange County, CA, Incorporate Culturally Sensitive Practices (N = 25)

Please rate the degree to which each statement applies to you:	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
I display pictures, posters, and other materials that reflect the cultures and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by my program or agency.	2.68	1.25
When using videos, films, or other media resources for education, treatment, or other interventions, I ensure that they reflect the cultures of children and families served by my program or agency.	3.80	1.00
I encourage and provide opportunities for children and their families to share experiences through storytelling, puppets, marionettes, or other props to support the “oral tradition” common among many cultures.	2.64	1.50
For children who speak languages or dialects other than English, I attempt to learn and use keywords in their language so that I am better able to communicate with them during assessment, treatment, or other interventions.	3.96	0.94
I use visual aids, gestures, and physical prompts in my interactions with children who have limited English proficiency.	4.56	0.58
When interacting with parents and other family members who have limited English proficiency, I always keep in mind that limitation in English proficiency is in no way a reflection of their level of intellectual functioning.	4.88	0.44
I understand the principles and practices of linguistic competency and apply them within my program or agency.*	4.08	1.02
I avoid imposing values that may conflict or be inconsistent with those of cultures or ethnic groups other than my own.	4.72	0.54
I advocate for the review of my program’s or agency’s mission statement, goals, policies, and procedures to ensure that they incorporate principles and practices that promote cultural diversity, cultural competence, and linguistic competence.	3.88	1.27
I understand that beliefs about mental illness and emotional disabilities are culturally based. I accept that responses to these conditions and related treatment/intervention are heavily influenced by culture.	4.40	0.71

Note: Measurement scale: 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always; *One participant did not answer this item.

Table 3

Levels of Training, Education, and Comfortability on Cultural Competency and Working with Diverse Families (N = 21)

Please rate the degree to which each statement applies to you:	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
The program or agency I work for provides training courses, workshops, or meetings on working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.	3.00	1.18
I feel supported by the program or agency I work for in regard to working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.	3.95	0.97
In my education, I was taught about culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families, and how to work with them.	3.81	0.98
I feel comfortable when working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.	4.10	0.70
I wish I was better prepared to work with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.	3.05	1.16

Note: Measurement scale: 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always.

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Appendix A

Self-Assessment Checklist for Personnel Providing Services and Supports to Children and Youth With Special Health Needs and Their Families

This instrument was developed by Tawara D. Goode of the Georgetown University Center for Child and Human Development. This version is adapted with permission from Promoting Cultural Competence and Cultural Diversity in Early Intervention and Early Childhood Settings (June 1989). It is available from the Web site of the National Center for Cultural Competence (<http://nccc.georgetown.edu/documents/ChecklistEIEC.pdf>).

Select A, B, or C for each numbered item listed:

A = Things I do frequently B = Things I do occasionally C = Things I do rarely or never

Physical Environment, Materials and Resources

- _____ 1. I display pictures, posters, and other materials that reflect the cultures and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by my program or agency.
- _____ 2. I [e]nsure that magazines, brochures, and other printed materials in reception areas are of interest to and reflect the different cultures of children and families served by my program or agency.
- _____ 3. When using videos, films, or other media resources for health education, treatment, or other interventions, I ensure that they reflect the cultures of children and families served by my program or agency.
- _____ 4. When using food during an assessment, I [e]nsure that meals provided include foods that are unique to the cultural and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by my program or agency.
- _____ 5. I [e]nsure that toys and other play accessories in reception areas and those used during assessment are representative of the various cultural and ethnic groups within the local community and the society in general.

Communication Styles

- _____ 6. For children who speak languages or dialects other than English, I attempt to learn and use key words in their language so that I am better able to communicate with them during assessment, treatment, or other interventions.
- _____ 7. I attempt to determine any familial colloquialisms used by children and families that may have an impact on assessment, treatment, or other interventions.
- _____ 8. I use visual aids, gestures, and physical prompts in my interactions with children who have limited English proficiency.
- _____ 9. I use bilingual staff members or trained/certified interpreters for assessment, treatment, and other interventions with children who have limited English proficiency.

_____ 10. I use bilingual staff members or trained/certified interpreters during assessments, treatment sessions, meetings, and for other events for families who would require this level of assistance.

11. When interacting with parents who have limited English proficiency I always keep in mind that:

_____ Limitation in English proficiency is in no way a reflection of their level of intellectual functioning.

_____ Their limited ability to speak the language of the dominant culture has no bearing on their ability to communicate effectively in their language of origin.

_____ They may or may not be literate in their language of origin or English.

_____ 12. When possible, I ensure that all notices and communiqués to parents are written in their language of origin.

_____ 13. I understand that it may be necessary to use alternatives to written communications for some families, as word of mouth may be a preferred method of receiving information.

Values and Attitudes

_____ 14. I avoid imposing values that may conflict or be inconsistent with those of cultures or ethnic groups other than my own.

_____ 15. In group therapy or treatment situations, I discourage children from using racial and ethnic slurs by helping them understand that certain words can hurt others.

_____ 16. I screen books, movies, and other media resources for negative cultural, ethnic, or racial stereotypes before sharing them with the children and their parents served by my program or agency.

_____ 17. I intervene in an appropriate manner when I observe other staff members or parents within my program or agency engaging in behaviors that show cultural insensitivity, bias, or prejudice.

_____ 18. I understand and accept that family is defined differently by different cultures (e.g., extended family members, fictive kin, godparents).

_____ 19. I recognize and accept that individuals from culturally diverse backgrounds may desire varying degrees of acculturation into the dominant culture.

_____ 20. I accept and respect that male–female roles in families may vary significantly among different cultures (e.g., who makes major decisions for the family, play, and social interactions expected of male and female children).

_____ 21. I understand that age and lifecycle factors must be considered in interactions with individuals and families (e.g., high value placed on the decisions of elders or the role of the eldest male in families).

_____ 22. Even though my professional or moral viewpoints may differ, I accept the family/parents as the ultimate decisionmakers for services and supports for their children.

_____ 23. I recognize that the meaning or value of medical treatment and health education may vary greatly among cultures.

_____ 24. I recognize and understand that beliefs and concepts of emotional well-being vary significantly from culture to culture.

_____ 25. I understand that beliefs about mental illness and emotional disability are culturally based. I accept that responses to these conditions and related treatment/interventions are heavily influenced by culture.

_____ 26. I accept that religion and other beliefs may influence how families respond to illnesses, disease, disability, and death.

_____ 27. I recognize and accept that folk and religious beliefs may influence a family's reaction and approach to a child born with a disability or later diagnosed with a physical/emotional disability or special health care needs.

_____ 28. I understand that traditional approaches to disciplining children are influenced by culture.

_____ 29. I understand that families from different cultures will have different expectations of their children for acquiring toileting, dressing, feeding, and other self-help skills.

_____ 30. I accept and respect that customs and beliefs about food, its value, preparation, and use are different from culture to culture.

_____ 31. Before visiting or providing services in the home setting, I seek information on acceptable behaviors, courtesies, customs, and expectations that are unique to families of specific cultures and ethnic groups served by my program or agency.

_____ 32. I seek information from family members or other key community informants that will assist in service adaptation to respond to the needs and preferences of culturally and ethnically diverse children and families served by my program or agency.

_____ 33. I advocate for the review of my program's or agency's mission statement, goals, policies, and procedures to ensure that they incorporate principles and practices that promote cultural diversity and cultural competence.

There is no answer key with correct responses. However, if you frequently responded "C," you may not necessarily demonstrate values and engage in practices that promote a culturally diverse and culturally competent service delivery system for children with disabilities or special health care needs and their families.

Appendix B

Survey Questionnaire Used in the Present Study

Part 1 – Demographic Questionnaire:

This section of the survey includes common demographic questions to obtain background information on participant gender, age, ethnicity, race, and education.

- 1) What is your gender?
 - a) Female
 - b) Male
 - c) Transgender
 - d) Not listed
 - e) I prefer not to answer.
- 2) What is your age?
 - a) 18-25
 - b) 26-35
 - c) 36-45
 - d) 46-65
 - e) 66 or older
- 3) Which category describes you (select all that apply)?
 - a) Black or African American
 - b) White (non-Hispanic/Latinx)
 - c) Hispanic/Latinx
 - d) Asian or Asian American
 - e) Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander
 - f) Native American
 - g) Other: _____
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - a) High school graduate, diploma, or the equivalent (e.g., GED)
 - b) Some college, no degree
 - c) Trade/technical/vocational training
 - d) Associate degree
 - e) Bachelor's degree (BA/BS)
 - f) Master's degree (MA/MS)
 - g) Doctorate degree (Ph.D./MD)
 - h) Other: _____

Part 2 – Working with Diverse Children and their Families Questionnaire:

This section of the survey includes statements aimed to evaluate participants' levels of competency in working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and families.

Please rate the degree to which each statement applies to you based on the scale below:

(1) - Never; (2) - Rarely; (3) - Sometimes; (4) - Often; (5) - Always

- 1) I display pictures, posters, and other materials that reflect the cultures and ethnic backgrounds of children and families served by my program or agency. ()
- 2) When using videos, films, or other media resources for education, treatment, or other interventions, I ensure that they reflect the cultures of children and families served by my program or agency. ()
- 3) I encourage and provide opportunities for children and their families to share experiences through storytelling, puppets, marionettes, or other props to support the "oral tradition" common among many cultures. ()
- 4) For children who speak languages or dialects other than English, I attempt to learn and use keywords in their language so that I am better able to communicate with them during assessment, treatment, or other interventions. ()
- 5) I use visual aids, gestures, and physical prompts in my interactions with children who have limited English proficiency. ()
- 6) When interacting with parents and other family members who have limited English proficiency, I always keep in mind that limitation in English proficiency is in no way a reflection of their level of intellectual functioning. ()
- 7) I understand the principles and practices of linguistic competency and apply them within my program or agency. ()
- 8) I avoid imposing values that may conflict or be inconsistent with those of cultures or ethnic groups other than my own. ()
- 9) I advocate for the review of my program's or agency's mission statement, goals, policies, and procedures to ensure that they incorporate principles and practices that promote cultural diversity, cultural competence, and linguistic competence. ()
- 10) I understand that beliefs about mental illness and emotional disabilities are culturally based. I accept that responses to these conditions and related treatment/intervention are heavily influenced by culture. ()

Part 3 – Levels of Training and Education Questionnaire:

This section of the survey includes statements aimed to evaluate participants' levels of training and education in working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.

Please rate the degree to which each statement applies to you based on the scale below:

(1) - Never; (2) - Rarely; (3) - Sometimes; (4) - Often; (5) - Always

- 1) The program or agency I work for provides training courses, workshops, or meetings on working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families. ()
- 2) I feel supported by the program or agency I work for in regard to working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families. ()
- 3) In my education, I was taught about culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families, and how to work with them. ()
- 4) I feel comfortable when working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families. ()
- 5) I wish I was better prepared to work with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families. ()

Part 4 - Open-Ended Questionnaire:

This section of the survey allows participants the option to comment further on their practices, training, and/or education in working with culturally and linguistically diverse children and their families.

- 1) Is there anything else you would like to share about your clinical practice as it pertains to working with culturally/linguistically diverse families?

- 2) Is there anything else you would like to share about your training or education as it pertains to working with culturally/linguistically diverse families?

- 3) Is there anything else you would like to share?